

Original Article

Determinants of Current Account Deficits in Pakistan: A Time Series Analysis

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Abstract

The current study identifies the effect of FDI, fiscal deficit, and exchange rate on current account deficit. This is an explanatory Time-Series study. Contribution of budget deficit, FDI and ER in current account deficit is explored using ARDL bound test model in the context of Pakistan. Annual data is used in this study, covering the period from 1991 to 2020. Empirical investigations are executed by employing E-Views. Regression analysis shows that budget deficit has positive impact on CAD but insignificant in long run. Real effective exchange rate and FDI exerted significant positive impact on CAD. Coefficient of interest rate is positive but insignificant in the long run. The current study discovered that exchange rate is the key variable which positively affects the CAD. Similarly, budget deficit shows positive association with CAD but insignificant in LR. The following recommendations are proposed on the basis of current findings and literature review. To improve the trade deficit efforts should be made by growing exports through introducing better quality products and by discovering new global avenues. To restrict imports, import substitute industry must be introduced in economy that will lead to reduce CAD.

Keywords: Current account deficit, Exchange rate, Foreign direct investment, Fiscal deficit.

INTRODUCTION

Current account deficit is the calculation of nation's international trade where the imports value of goods and services exceed the exports value of country. The correlation between the current account deficits and fiscal deficits has long been discussed in the literature. Additionally, it has been observed that countries which have comparatively higher FDs are also facing elevated CADs.

There are two theories mentioned in economic literature which demonstrate the association between current account and budget deficit. The first is Keynesian income-expenditure model that shows the positive correlation between these two deficits. A higher fiscal deficit is the result of tax cuts that leads to higher domestic income level and domestic absorption. Consequently, the increment in income will promote imports as compared to exports, which will lead to trade deficit and ultimately trade deficit.

Fleming, 1962 and Mundell, 1963 proposed a model which states second hypothesis that a higher FD will lead to increase in exchange rate and rate of interest. The increment in rate of interest results in direct foreign investment in countries. Which results inspire national currency and rise in demand and make import inexpensive and exports costlier. However, the currency appreciation will rise imports and broaden trade deficit.

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Contrary wise, the Ricardian Equivalence view disagrees with income-expenditure approach of Keynes. It postulates that, budget and current account deficit has no association in an open economy. Moreover, investment, the rate of interest or consumption will not be affected by governmental tax cut policy. Modigliani and Ando (1957) made assumption that the consumption patterns of consumers will depend upon life cycle hypothesis (HCH), which states that consumer present consumption based on its expected continuance earnings instead of present earnings as formulated by the Keynesian view. Additionally, the permanent revenue approach proposed by Friedman in 1957, postulates that only permanent rise in income will raise private consumption. Due to deficit financed government expenditure or tax cut policy there is temporary increase in income that will lead to private saving instead of expenditure (Barro, 1989, Wilson and Hashemzadeh, 2006).

The increasing current account deficit together with fiscal deficits has been major issue for policymakers in Pakistan. In other words, it is not compulsory to identify the linkage between trade and budget imbalances in an economy for the emphasis on decentralization, growth and free trade. (Aqeel and Nishat 2000).

Cerovic (2015), examined the data of 25 economies from the period of 1989 to 2013 and found that, decrease in production and investment created fiscal deficit and this brings to increase aggregate demand, which introduced current account deficit.

Furthermore, Litsios & Pilbeam (2017), applied ARDL model for three countries Greece, Portugal and Spain by using quarter data. The results confirmed the negative association between Investment and twin deficits in these economies

Burney and Yasmeen, (1989) tested Pakistan's statistics and observed a positive correlation between the interest rate and budget deficit from the period of 1970-71 toward 1988-89. Rosenweing and Tallman, 1993 also supported the hypothesis that increase in FD appreciated dollars in an economy and this situation creates TD in the country.

Flassbeck and Lapavitsas (2013) examine the Twin deficit for eurozone and argue that exchange rates perform a vital role to create imbalances in Eurozone. The results of study demonstrate that causal relationships are monodirectional and causation runs from REER to CAD and then the budget deficit.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Fiscal deficit and Current account deficit

Previous studies recommend four testable theories regarding twin deficits (TD). The primary is Keynesian income-expenditure model, and it postulates that, higher BD will cause a parallel growth in trade deficit (CAD). However, in different countries based on varied economic situations the effects and outcomes could be differing. Several empirical studies support this hypothesis.

Recent study explored that an economic system openness to financial market liberalization, trade and development significantly influenced long run economic growth. To a certain extent economic growth is essential for economic well-being to react to a degree of financial expansion. Furthermore, financial acceptance shows the financial system liberalization might additionally have an impact on financial market openness through numerous channels. (Salifu et al, 2024)

Rehman, Shamshir and Shakir (2020) employing Vector Error Correction, Johansen co-integration Model and Augmented Dickey-Fuller test to examine the double deficit hypothesis in SR and LR for Pakistan's economy. They concluded that rate of interest and money supply (MS) has negative relationship with twin deficit in LR while FDI and GDP have positive relationship in LR.

The second theory suggests the Ricardian Equivalence Hypothesis (REH). It states that, trade deficits and government budget deficits have no association in an open economy. A number of studies have been conducted to evaluate REH in term of twin deficit. Ratha (2009) explored that in the short period of time the twin-deficits condition exists in Indian economy. However, in the LR there is no relationship between government budget deficits and foreign trade deficits. Therefore, these results are in agreement with REH.

The third hypothesis is constructed on the causation in one direction flows from foreign trade deficit to fiscal deficit. On the basis of this, Alkswani (2000) employing annual data to inspect the correlation between these two deficits in Saudi Arabian economy and claims that, neither the Keynesian approach nor the REH is effective in oil economy. The application of the Johansen co-integration and error correction models (ECM) identifies correlation between twin deficits in short and long-run, but Granger test for causality declares that current account deficit causes fiscal deficit. Alkswani proclaims that revenue of export effects earning and spending of government and the exports of commodities and services and summarized that there is a significant and positive association found amid the two deficits and the direction of causality is moving from CAD to FD.

The final view is based on the bilateral causative association between CAD and budget deficit. Mukhtar, Zakaria and Ahmed (2007) examine the Double Deficit Phenomenon for Pakistan and argue that fiscal deficit, rate of exchange and interest rates play a significant role in interpreting the trade balance. They determine two-direction causation between fiscal and trade deficits.

Rate of interest and Current account Deficit

Mundell Fleming proposed the model (Fleming, 1962; Mundell, 1963), which states that higher FD brings to rise in ER and interest rate. The higher rate of interest will lead to capital inflow in country. Consequently, domestic demand will increase and appreciate the domestic currency and make imports inexpensive and exports costlier. However, the currency appreciation will rise imports and escalate current account deficit. Several researches have been conducted to evaluate the correlation of double deficit with interest rate.

Salvatore, (2006), has exposed that budget deficit increases interest rate. The higher rate of interest contributes to capital inflow in country and appreciates the national currency. However, the currency appreciation will raise imports and widen current account deficit. Similarly, Payesteh, (2008) examine the economy of US and demonstrated that BD caused capital inflows, CAD, as well as increased the rate of interest.

Foreign direct investment and Current account deficit

Fleming 1962 and Mundell 1963 proposed a model which states that a higher fiscal deficit brings to raise in exchange rate and rate of interest. The increment in rate of interest will results foreign direct investment in country. Consequently, increase in demand that appreciate domestic currency and make import inexpensive and export expensive. However, the currency appreciation will raise imports and worsened current account deficit. Several researches have been conducted to evaluate the relationship of twin deficit with foreign direct investment.

A research conducted by Corsetti and Muller, (2006) was an agreement with this argument and found the correlation among the FD, Investment and CAD. These outcomes demonstrated by employing VAR technique that used on the yearly data of the economies of UK, Australia, Canada and US.

Exchange rate and Current account deficit

Fleming 1962 and Mundell 1963 proposed a model which states that a higher fiscal deficit brings to raise in exchange rate and rate of interest. The increment in rate of interest will results foreign direct investment in country. Which results appreciation of national currency and rise in demand and make import inexpensive and export costlier? However, the currency appreciation will rise imports and widen current account deficit.

Trade flow is negatively associated with ER fluctuations. So, to hold stable ER, international exchange market involvement is considered beneficial for economic well-being and trade. But, the countries where ER fluctuations have positive relationship with trade, a fewer market involvement and well receptive ER could be relatively beneficial. (Usman, 2023)

Kim and Robini (2008) investigate the impact of FD on trade deficit and REER by employing the VAR Model. The outcome of the study showed that expansionary fiscal deficit shock devalues the REER and

improves the trade deficit. Increase in private saving and decline in investment play a crucial role to improve trade deficit.

Government in developing countries focus on ER policies to achieve the goal of restoring foreign trade imbalances. But, regardless of policy implications, many developing countries have not now significantly bridged the gap of foreign currency. (Dachito Chigeto, 2024)

Furthermore, Banday and Aneja (2019) examine the TD hypothesis and macroeconomic variables for Chinese economy by employing ARDL approach over the period of 1985-2016. The outcomes of the study shows that negative fiscal deficit shock reduces the trade balance and large FD shock increase the trade balance but the large instability in exchange and interest rate brings to deviate of these two deficits.

Research Hypothesis

- H1. Fiscal deficit has significant positive effect on CAD in Pakistan.
- H2. Real exchange rate has significant positive impact on CAD in Pakistan.
- H3. Foreign direct investment has significant positive impact on CAD in Pakistan.

Theoretical Framework

Figure: 1. Theoretical Framework of current studies

METHODOLOGY, MODEL SPECIFICATION, VARIABLES AND DATA

Method applied in this study is quantitative and based on Time-Series data. To achieve the objectives of the study secondary data was employed. Econometric models are used to derive result. ADF tests are employed to confirm the stationarity of the data. ARDL test model is used to examine the effect of variables on CAD with the reference of Pakistan. This model is also used to analyze relationship among CAD, ER, BD and FDI.

Data collection

Time-Series data is explanatory in nature. Contribution of budget deficit, exchange rate and FDI in current account deficit is explored using ARDL bound test model in the context of Pakistan. Yearly data is employed in present study, covering the period from 1991 to 2020. The time series data is collected from several reports of Pakistan Economic survey and World Development Indicators (WDI). Empirical investigations are executed by employing E-Views.

Model Specification

The conceptual and theoretical framework relating to BD, exchange rate and CAD can be sketched from empirical and theoretical literature. The Keynesian (or conventional) approach postulates that, a rise in FD will cause a parallel rise in CAD. Thomas and Abderrezak (1988) explained the correlation between government budget deficit, investment and saving and foreign trade deficit in the context of equation (1 and 2) the mathematical expression of conceptual framework is

$$CAD = f(BD, Intr, FDI, REER) \quad (1)$$

where,

CAD = annually % of the Current account deficit.

BD = annually % of the Budget deficit.

FDI = annually % of Foreign Direct Investment.

Intr = annually % of Real Interest rate

REER= annually % of Real effective exchange rate

The multivariable model of the study is,

$$CAD = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BD + \beta_2 Intr + \beta_3 FDI + \beta_4 REER + \mu_1 \quad (2)$$

Unit root test (stationary test) and Diagnostic Tests

Unit root test is applied on the Time-Series data to confirm the stationarity of the statistics. Stationarity defines that autocorrelation, mean, and variance are constant in time series data. Generally, major financial time series data are non-stationary and integrated. In case, non-stationary time series (X) shows to be differenced (d) times until approaching stationarity, then the time series is supposed to be integrated of order (d) represented by $X_t \sim I(d)$. Therefore, to evade false regression and the failure to account for the suitable dynamic specification, Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test has been employed to examine the stationarity of the statistics proposed by (Dickey and Fuller 1976).

Testing for Co-integration

More often Time-Series variables employed in the present research are non-static, there is probability that regression of any non-static variable on another non-stationary variable showed incorrect regression. Johansen Likelihood Ratio test is employed to measure the falseness in regression. LR test statistics computed t value is compared with critical values. As indicated by the test measures if the critical value is less than test statistics computed value, that results null hypothesis of no co-integration is rejected and this requires a LR association amongst the variables despite the fact that if variables are non-stationary exclusively.

The ARDL Bound Testing Approach to Co-integration

Various techniques are applied in quantitative study to investigate the long run correlation among variables. Co-integration methods have been presented by Engle-Granger (1987) and Phillips and Hansen (1990). Moreover, multivariate co-integration methods constructed by Johansen's (1995) required equal degree of integration for all the variables, *i.e.*, I (1). Therefore, these technique of co-integration are not suitable and cannot be used. Hence this study applied ARDL bounds test technique formulated by (Pesaran and Shin, 1995; Pesaran et al., 1996), is better than co-integration test. ARDL bounds test can be useful for those variables that showed different integration orders. Auto-regressive distributed lag bounds test approach employed to test the congregation LR relationship for the sample size from 1980 to 2020 by comparing F value counter to the top and bottom critical points. If upper critical values are less than F-statistics, it reflects the co-integration among the variables.

ESTIMATION ANALYSIS

UNIT ROOT TEST

It is important to confirm the order of integration and stationarity before evaluating the specified model. Augmented Dickey-Fuller method has employed in the current study to investigate the order of integration and stationarity of the macroeconomics variables. Findings of ADF technique demonstrate that

all the variables used in research are stationary at 1st difference while REER and CAD are stationary at level. It means fiscal deficit, foreign direct investment and rate of interest has a unit root problem at level. Real exchange rate and CAD is integrated at $I(0)$ and fiscal deficit, foreign direct investment and rate of interest is integrated at $I(1)$. However, at second difference no variable is integrated. ARDL bound Test is suitable technique for mixed order of co-integration among variables. Results of unit root have shown in Table 1.

Table No. 1: Unit-Root Estimation

Variables	level	Prob.	Level 1%	Level 5%	Level 10%	1 st difference	Prob.
CAD	-4.039973	0.0018	-3.610453	-2.938987	-2.607932	-4.039973	0.0039
FD	-2.514343	0.1197	-3.605593	-2.936942	-2.606857	-7.560569	0.0000
FDI	-2.860436	0.0593	-3.610453	-2.938987	-2.607932	-3.664319	0.0087
INT	-2.547290	0.1187	-3.769597	-3.004861	-2.642242	-4.122388	0.0046
REER	-4.560068	0.0007	-3.610453	-2.938987	-2.607932	-6.008455	0.0000

$$\ln CAD = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln BD + \beta_2 \ln Intr + \beta_3 \ln FDI + \beta_4 \ln REER + \mu_t$$

Figure: 2 Lag length selection

Figure 2 denotes optimal lag length of explanatory and dependent variables in the model. The above-mentioned figure shows that t AIC (3.92) of the estimated model.

Auto regressive distributed lag test

Null hypothesis is accepted when upper bound is greater than the F-value. It indicates that LR relationship is not observed among variables. Null hypothesis is rejected if upper bound is less than F-value. Table 2 demonstrates the results of bound test that F-statistics i.e. 8.028 > upper bound value (3.49) at significance of level 5 percent. Therefore, null hypothesis is not applicable instead an alternate is acceptable in the favor of co-integration at significance of level 5 percent. These results conclude that variable in ARDL technique are co-integrated and LR relationship found.

Table No. 2: ARDL Bound Test

F-Statistics		8.027967
Critical Value Bound		
Significance	10Bound (Lower)	11Bound (Upper)
10%	2.2	3.09
5%	2.56	3.49
2.5%	2.88	3.87

1% 3.29 4.37

Long run Representation

The next phase is to confirm the LR coefficients of IV after the confirmation of co-integration. Table 3 show the findings of LR coefficients that FD positively affect the CAD but insignificant in LR. The results show that current account deficit changed by 0.0095% due to 1.0% increment in fiscal deficit. Foreign direct investment and REER exerted positive and significantly influence the current account deficit. This demonstrates that CAD increase by 1.4% due to 1.0% increment in FDI and 1.0% increase in real effective exchange rate leads to 0.08% increment in CAD. Interest rate elasticity of trade deficit infers that 1.0 % increase in rate of interest resulted in 4.8% raise in current account deficit. Coefficient of interest rate is positive but insignificant in the long run.

$$CAD = -7.9164 + 0.0095(FD) + 1.4278(FDI) + 4.7794(INT) + 0.0817(REER)$$

Table No. 3: Coefficient (long run)

Depended Variable CAD

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
FD	0.009482	0.233823	0.040553	0.9681
FDI	1.427831	0.387646	3.683342	0.0015
INT	4.779371	8.330209	0.573740	0.5725
REER	0.081726	0.036825	2.219284	0.0382
C	-7.916424	3.579451	-2.211631	0.0388

Short run Representation

Table 4 illustrates that in short run FD has significant and positive impact on CAD. The results show that 0.475% increment in CAD due to 1.0% rise in FD in SR. REER has negative but significantly influence the CAD in short run. This illustrates that 1% increment in real effective exchange rate resulted in 0.077% decline in current account deficit in SR. Coefficient of estimation EC (-1) shows that adjustment speed to long run is 0.97. It illustrates that entire system is getting adjusted to long run equilibrium at the pace of 97%.

Table No. 4: Coefficient (short run)

Depended Variable CAD

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
D (CAD (-1))	0.418246	0.107171	3.902598	0.0009
D(FD)	0.475387	0.155925	3.048809	0.0063
D (FD (-1))	-0.545120	0.172904	-3.152740	0.0050
D(REER)	-0.077997	0.045985	-1.696154	0.1054
CointEq(-1)*	-0.974539	0.125593	-7.759495	0.0000

R-squared 0.805778

D.W 2.239150

Adjusted R-sq. 0.774703

Diagnostic Test

Table 5 shows the findings of diagnostic test that residual are normally distributed and successively un-correlated. Model has all properties that are desired. Hence, results are effective and consistent

Table No. 5: Diagnostic Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:

F-statistic	2.280738	Prob.	0.1310
Obs*R-squared	6.065396	Prob.	0.0482

Figure: 3 Normality test

Test for Stability

Figure 4 and 5 illustrate that projected model is specified and stable.

Figure: 5 Plot of QUSUMSQ

Figure: 4 Plot QUSUM

CONCLUSION

The current study was designed to explore the association among government budget deficit, exchange rate, CAD and foreign direct investment in SR as well as LR for the economy of Pakistan. The core objective of this investigation is to analyze the effect of government budget deficit, FDI and exchange rate on current account deficit from 1991 to 2020. Unit root test and ARDL bound test are used to examine the results. The empirical outcomes showed the association among the government budget deficit, exchange rate and trade deficit in Pakistan. In short term, fiscal deficit positively and significantly affects the current account deficit. In SR REER has negatively influenced trade deficit.

Government BD positively affects the CAD but insignificant in LR. On the other hand, interest rate is positive but found to be insignificant in the LR. Real effective ER and FDI exerted positive and significantly affect the current account deficit. Basically, Pakistan is an under developed economy with poor technological advancements. Capital inflow in an economy results in import of technology that leads to increase the import bill and widen the current account deficit.

RECOMMENDATION

The current study discovered that exchange rate and foreign direct investment is the key variable which positively affects the current account deficit. Similarly, government budget deficit shows positive association towards trade deficit but insignificant in LR. The following recommendations are proposed on the basis of current findings and literature review.

- Economy of Pakistan should focus to improve the government revenue and diminish non developmental expenses in fiscal deficit and improves trade surplus to progress terms of trade and balances of capital and current accounts.
- Government should control the exchange rate by different sources that will lead to reduce CAD.
- FDI should be export led sector that will help to reduce the trade deficit.
- The Pakistan's CA balance showed negative results over the last thirty years. To improve the trade deficit efforts should be made to improve the quality of goods by growing exports and by discovering new international markets and to restrict imports industry should be installed for import substitute product that will lead to reduce current account deficit.
- The government of Pakistan can increase the revenue collection by improving the tax collection policies that will help to improve the fiscal deficit

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